

THE INFLUENCE OF HUMAN RESOURCE COMPETENCE ON THE QUALITY OF GARMENT PRODUCTS AT PT. DAESE BANDUNG

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of human resource competence on the quality of garment products at PT. Daese located in Bandung. The research focuses on measuring components of competence such as knowledge, attitude, and skills of employees and their effect on improving the quality of garment products produced. A descriptive method with a quantitative approach was employed, involving 100 respondents from PT. Daese's employees through probability sampling using a likert scale. Data analysis via simple linear regression indicates that human resource competence exerts a positive and significant effect on product quality. This is demonstrated by a significance value of 0.000, which is below the 0.05 threshold, and a t-value of 11.829, exceeding the critical value of 1.98447, leading to acceptance of hypothesis H1 and rejection of H0. The determination coefficient of 0.588 suggests that human resource competence contributes 58.8% of the influence on product quality, while the remaining 41.2% is affected by other factors not studied here. These findings underscore the importance of developing human resource competence as a primary strategy to enhance garment product quality at PT. Daese.

Keywords: Human Resource Competence, Product Quality, Garment Industry

INTRODUCTION

The Garment Industry is a clothing production process from the manufacturing sector that produces apparel, the garment manufacturing process involves design, cutting, sewing, and quality inspection, aimed at meeting market or consumer needs. The production process in the garment industry is a series of stages carried out to produce quality products. The stages in the garment process from raw materials to

finished products, namely: 1) the process of selecting raw materials, is an important thing in production in the form of fabrics that factories choose based on quality, texture, color, and size, 2) the process of cutting fabric, the fabric is cut according to the design pattern of the product to be produced, cutting the fabric must be done carefully and accurately, 3) the sewing process, the fabric that has been cut with a predetermined pattern and design. the sewing stage must be done carefully and accurately, 3) the sewing process, the fabric that has been cut with a predetermined pattern and design, The sewing stage must be carried out with care and precision to produce quality products, 4) finishing process, including the stages of cleaning, drying, and polishing the product, 5) quality control process, to ensure that the product is in accordance with the factory's quality standards, this stage is very important to avoid defective products and ensure customer satisfaction, 6) packaging process, the product must be packaged neatly and according to predetermined standards.

PT Daese Garmin Bandung was established on March 15, 1988 as a joint venture with Segye Corporation (Daewo Group). Korea since the establishment of this company had stopped operating in 1992, then the parent company PT Metro Group took control of the company's management so that PT Daese Bandung was able to survive until now. PT Daese Garmin is engaged in a labor-intensive manufacturing industry that focuses on the production of suits such as blazers and pant which are sent to various countries namely the United States, Britain, Australia, Germany, South Korea, and the United Arab Emirates. To produce these products, the company uses raw materials sent directly from several countries such as India, Hong Kong, Korea, Shanghai, Canada and the USA. This proves the existence of PT Daese has been trusted to work with customers and suppliers who supply raw materials.

The products produced by the company are based on agreements from consumers both from the time of completion of manufacturing and the type of product that consumers want. PT Daese is one of the most reliable exporters of high-quality men's suits, PT Daese is also one of the bonded stockpiles.

The changing economy, and government policies especially in the field of labor which at that time was considered less favorable to the company, but PT. Daese continues to strive for continuous improvement especially in terms of quality and efficiency. This is what makes PT Daese still survive today. Competent human resources, supported by sophisticated equipment with modern technology is an absolute thing for PT. Daese to be able to compete in quality with other foreign-made

products.

The changing economy, and government policies, especially in the field of labor, which at that time were considered less favorable to the company, but PT Daese continues to strive for continuous improvement, especially in terms of quality and efficiency. This is what makes PT Daese still survive today. Competent human resources, supported by sophisticated equipment with modern technology is an absolute thing for PT. Daese to be able to compete in quality with other foreign-made products, but the level of employee attendance that has not been optimal results in ineffectiveness and efficiency that affects working time and the results obtained from the work performed. The low performance at PT Daese can be seen in the level of employee discipline, such as tardiness when entering work in the morning or entering work after a break, and before working hours end some employees have gone home before work time is not due. Every month these cases always occur, so that optimal use.

The production process in blezer manufacturing is very complex, with many complicated processes involved in realizing a product, to ensure each process runs smoothly and produces a perfect final product. The machine layout must be in accordance with each part of the process to be carried out in each production line, quality control must always check every process, so a skilled production manager or supervisor is needed so that the production process runs efficiently and on target.

Product quality at PT Daese in reality there are always product results that do not meet the expected specifications, this happens because of damage to the machine, there are fabrics that are different colors, dirty fabrics, and fabrics that are easily torn, causing the fabric produced to be damaged. Another problem is that there are defects at the end of sewing, holes hit by scissors, inappropriate tension, bubbling stitches, pocket depth not according to size, installation of buttons is not neat, installation of shoulders on the left and right blezers of different sizes, puckered stitches, missing stitches, fabric or thread clumping at the beginning or end of sewing, inconsistent fabric feed, and many more so that it is forced to reject or return. This study aims to determine how the competence of human resources on garment products at PT Daese Garmin because human resources are one of the factors determining the success or failure of a company, the excellence of a company's competitive quality is largely determined by the quality of qualified human resources. Competencies can include aspects of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and employee behavior, competencies are also

combined with soft skills, hard skills, social skills and mental skills. Soft skills show the intuition, sensitivity of human resources, hard skills reflect the knowledge and physical skills of human resources, social skills show the skills and social relations of human resources, while mental skills show the mentality of human resources. The importance of ensuring product quality is an important aspect in the sustainability of a company, companies that focus on improving product quality are usually able to build a positive image, increase consumer loyalty and succeed in the long run.

Through this research, it is hoped that an understanding of the garment industry can be obtained because it wants to know about the production process, and can be used as information for management in increasing the value of the company's products.

METHOD

The research method is a way to search, obtain or collect data, both primary and secondary data for solving various research problems. According to (Sugiyono, 2017: 2) research methods are scientific ways to obtain data with specific purposes and uses so that in turn they can be used to understand, solve and anticipate problems. So the selection of the right method is very important when conducting a study, because using the right method will help researchers to achieve a research goal.

Based on the variables studied, this type of research uses descriptive methods with a quantitative approach. According to (Sugiyono, 2017: 7) quantitative methods are defined as positivistic methods because they are based on the philosophy of positivism. This method is a scientific / scientific method because it fulfills scientific rules, namely concrete, measurable, rational, and systematic, this method is in the form of numbers and analysis using statistics. This quantitative descriptive research is used to examine the relationship between Human Resource Competencies and Garment Product Quality at PT Daese. The descriptive method begins with data collection, analysis and interpretation. Methods carried out through direct survey methods in the production field, case studies, behavior analysis and document analysis.

DATA ANALYST

Descriptive statistics are data analysis that aims to describe or explain the data that has been collected as it is, without intending to make conclusions that can be applied generally or thoroughly (Sugiyono, 2022: 147). The data analysis used is a questionnaire, distributed to employees of PT Daese in the supervisor section 25

people, leader 100 people, production sample 50 people, quality control 150 people and sewing line 1-6 480 people with a total of 100 respondents.

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

According to Sugiyono (2022: 188), simple linear regression analysis is used to determine the effect or relationship between independent variables and a dependent variable. This regression analysis is used to test how the influence of each independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y) is formulated in the form of an equation as follows:

$Y = a + bX$ Description:

Y : Dependent variable (dependent variable)

a: constant (value of Y if X = 0)

X : Independent variable (free variable)

b: regression coefficient (positive or negative influence)

Research Location

PT Daese Garmin is located at Jl. Ibrahim Adjie No. 90 kebon waru, Batununggal District, Bandung City 40272, West Java Province.

DATA ANALYSIS COLLECTION TECHNIQUES

Statistical analysis aims to provide an overview of respondents' perceptions of human resource competency variables (X) and product quality (Y) at PT Daese Garmen.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data processing, it shows that human resource competence in garment products at PT Daese has a positive influence. This means that the better the competence of human resources owned by an employee, the more progress the company will have. But there is the lowest score from the questionnaire results, which is 69.4%, indicating that there are challenges in completing work quickly and on time. This can be caused by several factors such as employee absences, delays

in goods, unequal fabric colors, damaged machines that cause many problems such as sewing threads often breaking during sewing, needles often breaking and causing defects in fabrics, and others. This causes obstruction of the production rate.

Based on the results of the analysis of product quality at PT Daese garment, it shows that the results of the questionnaire on the quality of PT Daese's products with the highest score with a score of 87% which is included in the very good category, with the question, the product design of PT Daese's blezer is very attractive and follows fashion trends. This reflects a strong aesthetic appeal, PT. Daese is also the best maker of men's suits and women's suits, PT. Daese products are in accordance with market and buyer demand. PT. Daese also implements finished goods storage management with good technology, making it easier when stuffing for export.

Based on data analysis, the effect of human resource competence on product quality at PT Daese. The results concluded that the t value of 11.829 is greater than t table 1.98447, so H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted. This shows that there is statistical significance in the human resource competency variable, with a statistical significance value on the human resource competency variable, with a significance value of 0.000 less than 0.05. Strengthening the conclusion that human resource competencies contribute significantly to product quality at PT Daese. The coefficient of determination is 58.8% of product quality, while the remaining 41.2% is estimated by other factors not discussed in this study.

REFERENCE

- Anwar, K et al (2020). Human Resource Managemant 5.0 Digitalisasi Sumber Day Manusia. CV Media Sains indonesia.
- Daga , R. (2017). Citra, Kualitas, dan Kepuasan Pelanggan. (cet ke-1). Global Research And Consulting Institute.
- Daryanto, (2021). Manajemen Produksi. (cet ke-1). Yrama Widya.
- Hartanto, (2009). Paradigma Baru Manajemen Indonesia: Menciptakan Nilai Dengan Bertumpu Pada Kebijakan Dan Potensi Insani.(cet ke-1). PT. Mizan Pustaka.
- Hidayatullah, et al. (2023). Metodologi Penelitian Pariwisata. (cet ke-1). Uwais

Inspirasi Indonesia.

Hutapea & Thoha, (2008). Kompetensi Plus Teori, Desain, Kasus Dan Penerapan Untuk HR Serta Organisasi Yang Dinamis. PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.

Rahadi, R. (2021) .Kompetensi Sumber Daya Manusia (cet-ke1). CV. Lentera Ilmu Madani.

Rusdiana, A & Ibrahim. T. (2020). Manajemen Pengembangan Human Capital. (cet-ke-1). Yrama Widya.

Sugiyono. (2022). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, Dan R&D. (cet ke-29).Alfabeta CV.